

The Dynamics of In-store Advertising on Customer Purchase Decision

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Abstract

Advertising induces the purchase situation most likely to be more convincing in day-to-day affairs. Customers gain from in-store advertisements in the purchasing ambiance, regardless of whether they are pre-set to a competitor's brand. When purchasing, a consumer with a favorable brand image and positive brand beliefs is typically influenced by in-store advertisements to tolerate risk or vulnerability. In many areas, in-store advertisements influence consumer decisions through fashion, design, and salesmanship. Owing to the ideology, this study aimed to determine how in-store advertisements affected customers' desire or decision to buy in a retail setting. With 410 (random) respondents' opinions from 40 outlets/one-stop shops in the Dhaka, Chittagong, and Feni districts through confirmatory factor analysis, factors such as in-store advertisements and customers' purchase decisions, brand selections, attitudes, fashion, design, and salesman's function were shown to have a discernible influence with each other, based on their respective relationships. Ultimately, this research showed how in-store advertisements affect customers' exploratory and purchasing decisions in retail. Ultimately, these justifications will represent the new aesthetic and the significance of in-store advertisements for customers' learning paradigms concerning retail purchases.

Keywords: *In-store advertising; Purchase decision; Retail marketing; Retail store; Brand.*

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Introduction

One of the most common strategies marketing managers use to develop brands is advertising, which enhances perceived quality, forges favorable brand connections, and strengthens customer loyalty [1]. Manufacturers then use advertising as a tactical tool in retail for store brands [2], even for national and private brands [3]. Nonetheless, manufacturers and retailers are becoming more interested in in-store marketing as a brand's market share increases [4]. Thus, the impacts of store brands and their

advertising under marketing communication platforms or mix have been the subject of several research studies [5-6]. According to Raju et al. [7], Narasimhan and Wilcox [8], Morton and Zettelmeyer [9], Sayman et al. [10], and others, the primary focus has been on comprehending integrated marketing mix, such as pricing competition among different companies in an advertising message. However, several empirical studies indicate that, whether through internal or external advertising, marketing initiatives that strengthen manufacturers' brand equity are crucial to defeating private labels [11-12].

Even so, it is inevitable that businesses must combine in-store data from all of their channels in order to improve the entire customer journey [13]. Whether or not businesses are investing, their natural and direct interactions with customers through the direct-to-consumer (DTC) model play a significant role in this framework as part of the revenue mix [14]. This direct sales strategy is becoming increasingly important as an expansion of the companies' DTC channels, where brands plan to open their retail shops for a better customer experience or to collect customer data and build suitable brand relationships with customers [15]. According to Kumar et al. [16], this presents a chance or a solid strategy for a new D2C brand; nonetheless, given the rivalry from the retail behemoths.

Recent studies have suggested employing brand or market-level advertising as better tools for fashion, design, brand or store image, and salesmanship [2, 4, 17]. This tactic is constrained by everyday worries about the demand for advertising against price equilibrium [18] for the manufacturers due to a source of random variation or case-specific efficacy of advertising. For instance, Sethuraman et al. [19] observe that advertising elasticity decreases with time. Thus, this doubt has now been embedded in the enthusiasm for justifying the efficacy of in-store ads in retail settings and enhancing the intricate dynamics of in-store advertising and its profound influence on the purchasing decisions of customers frequenting private stores. To achieve this overarching issue, the authors have outlined two specific goals. Firstly, the study

investigates the roles of store loyalty, brand attitudes, and salesman advocacy in shaping predetermined brand choices and instantaneous decision-making processes. By scrutinizing these factors, the research aims to unravel the underlying mechanisms guiding consumer behavior within the retail environment. Secondly, the study seeks to assess the tangible impact of in-store advertisements on customer preferences. Through meticulous analysis of customer responses, the research endeavors to pinpoint the key determinants influencing the effectiveness of in-store ads, thereby facilitating the refinement of advertising strategies tailored to meet consumers' evolving needs and preferences. So, these aims are substantiated by the research questions: *“How do store loyalty, brand attitudes, and salesman advocacy influence predetermined brand choices and instant decision-making processes among customers in private stores? Moreover, what are the key factors shaping customer preferences regarding in-store advertising, and how do these factors impact the effectiveness of in-store ads?”* Ultimately, this study aspires to furnish invaluable insights that can empower retailers to optimize their marketing efforts and enhance the overall shopping experience for their clientele.

Likewise, the choice of sample area for this research on the impact of store advertising on customer purchase decisions was driven by several key factors. First, private stores or superstores constitute a significant retail industry segment, serving a diverse customer base and offering a wide range of products and brands. This makes them ideal settings for studying the dynamics of in-store advertising, which directly influences consumer behavior within this retail environment. Moreover, the accessibility of private stores to a broad demographic range enhances the representative sample, allowing for more comprehensive analysis across different customer segments. Additionally, the variability in product offerings and store layouts within these establishments provides ample opportunities to explore the effectiveness of various advertising strategies and their impact on consumer decision-making processes.

As for contributions, this study provides valuable insights into the psychological and behavioral aspects influencing purchase decisions in private stores/superstores by shedding light on the intricate relationships among these factors by understanding the interplay between store loyalty, brand attitudes, and salesman advocacy, which are pivotal in shaping consumer choices within the retail environment. However, assessing the effectiveness of in-store advertising and identifying key factors influencing customer preferences offer valuable insights for retailers seeking to optimize their marketing strategies. In this case, the impact of in-store ads on shaping consumer

perceptions, attitudes, and purchase intentions, thereby aiding in developing targeted and effective advertising campaigns, is possible. Moreover, the actionable insights for retailers to enhance the effectiveness of their in-store advertising initiatives drive sales, improve customer satisfaction, and foster brand loyalty within the competitive retail landscape.

Lastly, conducting research within private stores offers practical advantages, such as observing real-time consumer behavior in a naturalistic setting, thereby enabling researchers to gather contextually relevant data without artificial constraints or biases. This comprehensive approach is reflected in the outlined section progression, which encompasses an in-depth exploration of the literature review, methodology, data analysis, discussion of findings, and concluding remarks, thereby contributing valuable insights to both theory and practice in retail marketing.

In-store Advertising, Attitude, Brands and Purchase Decision

Prior research proves that attitude analysis technology may be valuable for examining consumers' psychology when choosing brands or items [20]. Owing to these views, modifying attitudes through in-store advertising is an excellent tool for researching consumer psychology connected to branding since it is susceptible to brain reactions to stimuli (brands). According to Solomon et al. [21], consumer attitudes have behavioral, emotive, and cognitive components. More specifically, the cognitive component involves evaluating a consumer's knowledge and beliefs about a product (brand); the affective component reflects the consumer's psychological reaction to a product; and the behavioral component is the outward manifestation of the consumer's intention to choose a product. Empirically, in many nations, different theories (e.g., theory of planned behavior) [22-23] are frequently employed to gauge consumers' intentions to purchase goods [24] to justify mutual relations, satisfaction, and loyalty irrespective of the advertising platform (whether to internal or external).

However, merchants of private labels may be more at risk from brand loyalty [25] compared to national brands that (historically) benefited from far higher consistency in the favorable attitudes, preferences, and repurchases resulting from brand loyalty among their customers. According to Breneiser and Allen [26], perceived quality rather than actual quality often has a more significant influence on consumers' buying decisions, which puts private labels at risk as they compete for the same customer base. Finally, private label merchants run the same risk of jeopardizing their relationship with national brand manufacturers when they use more forceful marketing strategies. Ironically, one of the main factors influencing consumers' choice of private

labels is in-store advertising, highlighting the differences in value and price between private labels and national brands [27]. Moreover, national brands' marketing campaigns usually help the whole product category, including the related private labels [27], irrespective of private in-store advertising. Therefore, the synergistic advertising interaction between national brands and private labels is extraordinarily intricate for customer response.

In-store Advertising, Fashion, Design, and Salesmanship

Studies examining how in-store advertising affects customers' decisions to buy in fashion, design, and salesmanship offer valuable insights into the behavior of consumers and retail tactics [28]. Research shows in-store advertising significantly influences customers' attitudes and actions [29]. As to Iyer et al. [30], extended exposure to retail ads and promotional activities tends to elevate the probability of impulsive purchases. Furthermore, the atmosphere produced by components like lighting, music, and product displays can arouse favorable feelings and encourage impulsive purchases [31]. This implies that efficient in-store advertising fosters a positive shopping experience that promotes customer engagement and loyalty and increases sales.

Furthermore, the literature emphasizes how critical it is to comprehend how customers' perceptions and the physical characteristics of the retail environment interact [32]. Customers' perceptions of retail space and its offers are influenced by several factors, including room size, shop layout, and visual complexity [33]. For instance, a well-thought-out layout that makes products visible and easy to navigate may improve the shopping experience and positively affect buying decisions [18]. Similarly, aesthetic details like color schemes and architectural patterns may help create an aesthetically pleasing setting that draws in and keeps consumers [16].

Additionally, research highlights how salesmanship influences sales performance and consumer engagement [18]. Successful sales techniques include building rapport and trust and convincing clients to buy [13]. According to research, salespeople's social interactions and personal qualities affect how satisfied customers are and how they perceive them [4]. According to Khan et al. [28], sales associates who exhibit product expertise, professionalism, and attention have more potential to influence client perceptions and boost sales conversion rates favorably. Studies on in-store advertising and salesmanship often highlight the significance of developing immersive retail experiences that engage with customers and foster meaningful relationships between companies and consumers in the fashion and design business [34].

With the discovery of the power of in-store promotions, extensive research reveals compelling insights into customer behavior during events versus non-event periods, shedding light on key factors that drive sales. Within the captivating ambiance of the in-store advertising, customer attitude, fashion, design, purchase decision, brand image, and salesmanship exert a magnetic pull on shoppers, igniting higher sales than external campaigns. There is a significant variation in the relative reaction to the factors between customers. Therefore, it is crucial to pinpoint the factors that influence the direction of in-store advertising to choose how to launch them better.

Methodology

Whether outdoor or in-store, advertising entices consumers to buy products from well-known brands or rival companies. The initial survey aims to determine the influence of in-store advertisements on consumers' buying intentions or decisions in the retail industry. Due to the study's goals, it is intended to gather data on consumers' specific selection criteria, particularly concerning brand image, favorable brand belief, and enduring risk/vulnerability.

Idea Validation and Pilot Testing

According to the nature of the research topic, the early phases of the study included training field personnel, developing survey procedures, conducting exploratory site visits, and surveying secondary data. This study's primary factors were salesperson advocacy, brand views, design, and store fashion loyalty. More precisely, desk research was conducted to examine secondary literature to build the methodology when design survey methodologies, analytical tools, and essential results about the primary variable influencing purchase choice were prioritized. At this point, pilot surveys were conducted to offer recommendations and hints on potential questions for more formal surveys using questionnaires based on customer choice criteria. A pilot testing approach including 150 respondents' judgments from around 20 outlets/one-stop stores in Feni districts was designed to validate concepts by random selection. In order to get preliminary information on customer preferences for decisions, data from pilot surveys were processed and analyzed. This information will serve as a benchmark for full-fledged survey questions on static and dynamic patterns of purchase preference.

Hypothesis

Null hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant correlation between in-store advertising and the variables of fashion, design, salesmanship, attitude, brands, and purchase decisions.

Alternative hypothesis (H_1): There is a significant correlation between in-store advertising and at least one of the variables of fashion, design, salesmanship, attitude, brands, and purchase decision.

Questionnaire and Sample Size

Surveys on static and dynamic changes in consumer choice were conducted after pilot testing. It was then determined whether the data and questions were appropriate for the stated analysis and standard. The questionnaire was completed in this respect. Survey methods such as (a) questionnaire surveys, (b) direct observations, and (c) semi-structured interviews were used to gather data. The specifics of the in-store advertisement and the store's accessibility determined the use of the cluster sampling approach. Conversely, the quantity and scope of the stores dictate the proportion of actual consumers, level of engagement, and store satisfaction. Marketing surveys were created for general consumer engagement to evaluate the degree of marketing efficiency and create more effective in-store advertisements. More precisely, 410 responses were deemed legitimate following editing and mistake checking out of the 500 respondents' initial judgment gathered by random selection from 40 outlets/one-stop shops situated in the locations.

Data Analysis, Results, and Discussion

The researcher has used structural equation modeling and confirmatory factor analysis to evaluate direct correlations among the variables under study [35]. These analyses have been carried out using AMOS 22 and SPSS 22. These analyses aim to provide a reliable evaluation of the consumer's antecedents of purchasing choice, particularly in Bangladeshi retail services, hence aiding in the understanding of model fit

Factor Analysis

After that, factor analysis was used to examine the data using SPSS 22.0. To categorize variables based on the amount of correlation among the items for the prior and find relationships among the variables for the latter, two types of factor analysis were used: exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA).

Sampling Adequacy of Data

The Table 1 data's sampling adequacy is shown by the KMO value of 0.833

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.833
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	14990.202
	df	734
	Sig.	.000

Table 1. KMO and Bartlett's test

Component	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	13.205	32.762	32.762	5.482	14.226	14.226
2	5.102	11.651	44.412	5.404	12.237	28.452
3	4.105	8.705	53.117	5.208	11.732	40.689
4	2.103	5.556	58.673	4.875	10.011	50.7
5	2.001	5.086	63.759	3.065	6.501	57.201
6	1.229	4.323	68.082	1.753	3.382	60.583
7	1.102	2.761	70.843	1.279	2.789	63.372

Table 2. Total variance explained

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Principal component analysis has been applied once again to the variables. Table II displays the rotating sum of squared loadings, the Eigenvalues, and the proportion of total variance. The principal component analysis-derived factor matrix has furthermore undergone Varimax Rotation. Table II shows that eight factors were kept after Eigenvalues were examined. The total variance for these parameters is 13.205%, 5.102%, 4.105%, 2.103%, 2.001%, 1.229%, and 1.102%. This suggests that the remaining variance is explained by other factors, with the overall variance accounted for by all eight components being 83.867%.

Reliability

The various constructs were calculated using SPSS 22’s reliability technique to get the reliability coefficient. The total construct utilized in this investigation has reliabilities higher than the conventional set of 0.70 [36]. In Table III, the range of Cronbach’s alpha indicates the degree of dependability for the research variables, ranging from $\alpha = 0.862$ to $\alpha = 0.913$.

Items	Cronbach’s Alpha Based on Standardized Items
Purchase decision	0.880
Fashion	0.874
Brand	0.862
In-store ad	0.913
Design	0.879
Attitude	0.906
Salesman	0.895

Table 3. Reliability Statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Purchase decision	1	5	3.397	0.865	0.251	0.11	0.248	0.22
Fashion	1	5	3.219	0.939	0.215	0.11	0.023	0.22
Brand	1	5	3.352	0.911	0.353	0.11	0.772	0.22
In-store ad	1	5	3.774	0.921	0.251	0.11	0.089	0.22
Design	1	5	3.197	0.735	0.312	0.11	0.438	0.22
Attitude	1	5	3.408	0.679	0.408	0.11	0.306	0.22
Salesman	1	5	3.097	0.781	0.592	0.11	0.948	0.22

Table 4. Descriptive statistics

Normality Test

The previous data established criteria for determining normality through Kurtosis and Skewness were as follows: +/- 3 and +/- 10 for Kurtosis and Skewness, respectively, were the threshold values for justification [37], with positive and negative values indicating the direction of positive and negative relations, respectively [38]. Furthermore, Table 4 shows that salesmen (3.097) have the lowest mean and in-store ads (3.774) have the highest, with fashion having the biggest dispersion (0.939). The range of the Skewness and Kurtosis is between 0.023 and 0.772, although it stays within the predicted bounds. Hence, the data is normally distributed.

Multi-collinearity Test

Pearson Correlation analysis has been used to examine the problem of multi-collinearity with a score of more than +/- 0.90 to assess the linear link among predictors and the degree of relationship [39].

	Purchase decision	In-store ad	Brand	Fashion	Design	Attitude	Salesman
Purchase decision	1.000	0.545	0.661	0.382	0.369	0.506	0.351
In-store ad	0.545	1.000	0.563	0.440	0.392	0.633	0.350
Brand	0.661	0.563	1.000	0.386	0.397	0.473	0.403
Fashion	0.382	0.440	0.386	1.000	0.380	0.558	0.339
Design	0.369	0.392	0.397	0.380	1.000	0.515	0.304
Attitude	0.506	0.633	0.473	0.558	0.515	1.000	0.504
Salesman	0.351	0.350	0.403	0.339	0.304	0.504	1.000

Table 5. Correlation

The maximum coefficient value from the correlation matrix's Table 5, 0.66, is not very close to the limit of multi-collinearity problems. Again, the correlation coefficients indicate the strength and direction of the relationship between in-store advertising and the other variables.

I. Purchase Decision:

- Correlation coefficient ($r = 0.545, p < 0.05$): There is a moderate positive correlation between in-store advertising and purchase decision. This suggests that purchase decisions also tend to increase as in-store advertising increases.

II. Brand:

- Correlation coefficient ($r = 0.563, p < 0.05$): There is a moderate positive correlation between in-store advertising and brand perception. This implies that as in-store advertising increases, consumers' perceptions of the brand also tend to increase.

III. Fashion:

- Correlation coefficient ($r = 0.440, p < 0.05$): There is a moderate positive correlation between in-store advertising and fashion appeal. This suggests that perceptions of fashion appeal also tend to increase as in-store advertising increases.

IV. Design:

- Correlation coefficient ($r = 0.392, p < 0.05$): A moderate positive correlation exists between in-store advertising and design perception. This indicates that design quality perceptions also increase as in-store advertising increases.

V. Attitude:

- Correlation coefficient ($r = 0.633, p < 0.05$): There is a strong positive correlation between in-store advertising and consumer attitude. This suggests that as in-store advertising increases, consumers' attitudes towards the product or store also tend to become more positive.

VI. Salesmanship:

- Correlation coefficient ($r = 0.350, p < 0.05$): There is a weak positive correlation between in-store advertising and salesmanship perception. This implies that as in-store advertising increases, perceptions of salesmanship also tend to increase, but the relationship is not as strong as with other variables.

Here, all the correlation coefficients indicate positive correlations between in-store advertising and fashion, design, salesmanship, attitude, brands, and purchase decisions, and all have p-values less than 0.05, indicating statistical significance. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1). Hence, the evidence supports the idea that in-store advertising has a meaningful relationship with consumer perceptions and purchase decisions. Ultimately, the results suggest that in-store advertising significantly correlates with various aspects such as purchase decisions, brand perception, fashion appeal, design perception, attitude, and salesmanship. Businesses should consider the impact of in-store advertising on these factors to effectively influence consumer behavior and improve overall sales performance.

Common Method Bias

Due to the recommendation of Hair, Hult, Ringle, Sarstedt, and Thiele [40] [with the condition of less than 50% of total variance explained by a factor], the un-rotated

Harman's single factor analysis was conducted to assess the biases of the standard method. It was discovered that 13.205% of the total variance explained by one factor satisfied the requirement of less than 50%.

Demographic Analysis

37% of the 410 legitimate survey respondents were female, while 63% of the respondents were male. Most participants were between 20 and 50+ and purchased many from retail establishments. The most significant number of participants was between the ages of 30 and 40, accounting for 43%, followed by those between the ages of 40 and 50, 10 percent, and those between the ages of 20 and 30.

Convergent Validity Analysis

In convergent validity, when the threshold value is at least 0.50, a greater loading (more than 0.70) indicates a better likelihood of acceptance [41]. The minimal allowable value from the standpoint of factor loading is 0.60, which meets the requirement as stated by previous research.

The minimum acceptable limit was more than or equal to 0.50 for the composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) values for the variables that were chosen [42]. Once more, achieving no values below 0.50 indicates acceptable internal consistency, which resolves this problem.

Items	CR	AVE
Instore ad	0.88	0.64
Purchase decision	0.86	0.56
Attitude	0.87	0.62
Brand	0.83	0.50
Design	0.82	0.52
Fashion	0.84	0.51
Salesman	0.86	0.60

Table 6. Composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE)

Fornell and Lacker [43] recommended considering AVE values less than 0.50 if CR is more than 0.70; however, the value of AVE should be more than the correlation value of that variable with other variables to prevent the problem of discriminant validity. The variables were unimportant in every case by meeting the criteria listed in Table 6.

Discussion

The findings of this research significantly contribute to the existing body of knowledge regarding consumer behavior, particularly in the context of decision-

making processes influenced by store loyalty, brand attitudes, salesman advocacy, and in-store advertising. Understanding the intricate dynamics and factors at play when consumers navigate product choices through in-store advertising is crucial [44]. This study utilized an experimental approach to identify the determinants impacting consumers' product choices and the subsequent behavioral responses triggered by in-store advertising stimuli. It is a foundational exploration for investigating various products and brands to gain fresh insights into consumer behavior dynamics across different product categories and brand types [45].

Perceived behavioral control, defined as customers' assessments of their ability to perform a specific behavior, emerges as a critical factor in evaluating the effectiveness of in-store advertising. This concept encompasses perceptions of resource availability and opportunities, including the influence of advertising, among other control beliefs [46]. Perceived behavioral control was operational through several quantifiable variables, including switching costs, procedural switching costs, and relational costs, to assess its impact [47-49]. The internalized attitudes guiding customers' purchasing decisions, even when they deviate from their initial preferences, served as a proxy for perceived behavioral control in this study.

Previous research indicates that brand preference formation is significantly influenced by rational and emotional factors within the human decision-making process [50]. These findings support the notion that emotions play a pivotal role in consumer decision-making, with customers often making choices driven by emotional attachment and adherence to personal values [51]. Again, the study's results demonstrate the positive impact of in-store advertising on utilitarian and hedonic shopping objectives, aligning with the propositions of Babin et al. [52]. In-store advertisements effectively stimulate impulsive purchases to fulfill emotional needs, particularly among hedonic buyers, contingent upon their purchasing ideology [53]. These findings underscore consumers' inclination to prioritize immediate emotional gratification, leading to impulsive buying behavior, while external stimuli or emotional impulses less sway those with utilitarian purchasing tendencies [54]. Ultimately, customer service environments, whether in-store or online, play a significant role in attracting customers and influencing their purchasing decisions [55]. In-store elements, including ambiance and associated factors, significantly shape customers' perceptions of their shopping experiences, subsequently influencing their intentions to stay longer and make purchases [56]. Despite the rise of online shopping, in-store advertisements remain indispensable for driving foot traffic to brick-and-mortar establishments and increasing customer engagement and sales.

Theoretical and Practical Implications

Qualitative and quantitative surveys integrated geographical and relevant data and provided actionable insights for marketers, policymakers, new investors/store owners, and stakeholders. The aim is to enhance visibility and exert direct influence by strengthening capabilities through education, communication, and leveraging indigenous in-store persuasion models tailored for retail shop development across local, regional, and international markets. These efforts are expected to yield significant shifts in sales growth, particularly attributed to dynamic changes in spending patterns among urbanized middle-class and upper-class consumers. The anticipated outcomes of this research will amalgamate scientific insights with technological innovations to augment consumer behavior understanding, specifically in the realm of in-store advertising's impact on purchase decisions, which presents substantial opportunities for consumer goods companies worldwide.

In addition, this study advocates for a sustainable development framework applicable to developed and developing nations such as Bangladesh. Retail owners, government agencies, regulatory bodies, and other stakeholders can potentially adopt this framework to harness the power of effective advertising and formulate coordinated strategies to tackle various challenges, thereby fostering growth in this sector. This trajectory is poised to attract investments, elevate service standards to international levels, foster knowledge transfer, introduce advanced technologies, and instill a sense of pride. Moreover, under this framework, urbanization and peri-urbanization trends will persist, accompanied by shifts in demographic dynamics, increased employment and income levels, and a more educated, youthful population, all of which will profoundly shape consumer purchasing behavior.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study sheds light on the multifaceted impacts of in-store advertising on various aspects of consumer behavior, including purchase decisions, attitudes, design perception, brand image, fashion preferences, and salesmanship. Through this empirical research, we have explored the intricate dynamics influencing customers' responses to in-store advertisements during peak shopping hours. Our findings underscore the growing significance of in-store advertising as a strategic tool for retailers to enhance customer engagement, drive sales, and shape brand perceptions. The increasing market share of store brands globally highlights the evolving landscape of retail marketing, where retailers leverage innovative technologies and contemporary marketing techniques to stay competitive and meet the evolving demands of consumers. Consequently, retailers can affect producers- both big and small

manufacturers. Due to the difficulties in gathering information from various retail locations, similar topics may be the focus of future studies, which may also evaluate the functions and effects of advertising from the perspectives of producers and retailers. In-store advertisements draw attention even when customers are not looking for innovative products with fresh styles and designs. The best-case scenario for this initiative was thought to be piquing customers' interest in in-store advertisements with the extra benefit of helping businesses boost sales. To sum up, the variety of advertising materials and planned and adjusted interests are the foundation for the flexibility and efficacy of in-store advertisements in retail stores.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Author Contribution

Conceptualization, methodology, literature review, resources, M.A.K., A.A.C., M.M.H., and M.R.; writing—original draft preparation, writing—review and editing, M.A.K., M.M.H., A.A.C. and M.R.; Software, data entry and analysis,—M.A.K., M.R., M.M.H., and A.A.C.; Revisions based on reviewers' comments—M.A.K., M.M.H., A.A.C. and M.R.

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